

Turbulent dynamics and whole-brain modeling: towards new clinical applications for traumatic brain injury

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) is a prevalent disorder mostly characterized by persistent
4 impairments in cognitive function that poses a substantial burden on caregivers and the healthcare
5 system worldwide. Crucially, severity classification is primarily based on clinical evaluations,
6 which are non-specific and poorly predictive of long-term disability. In this Mini Review, we
7 first provide a description of our model-free and model-based approaches within the turbulent
8 dynamics framework as well as our vision on how they can potentially contribute to provide
9 new neuroimaging biomarkers for TBI. In addition, we report the main findings of our recent
10 study examining longitudinal changes in moderate-severe TBI (msTBI) patients during a one
11 year spontaneous recovery by applying the turbulent dynamics framework (model-free approach)
12 and the Hopf whole-brain computational model (model-based approach) combined with in silico
13 perturbations. Given the neuroinflammatory response and heightened risk for neurodegeneration
14 after TBI, we also offer future directions to explore the association with genomic information.
15 Moreover, we discuss how whole-brain computational modeling may advance our understanding
16 of the impact of structural disconnection on whole-brain dynamics after msTBI in light of our
17 recent findings. Lastly, we suggest future avenues whereby whole-brain computational modeling
18 may assist the identification of optimal brain targets for deep brain stimulation to promote TBI
19 recovery.

20 **Keywords:** traumatic brain injury, nonlinear brain dynamics, turbulence, whole-brain modeling, neuroimaging biomarkers, stratified
21 neurology

1 INTRODUCTION: THE TURBULENT DYNAMICS FRAMEWORK AND WHOLE-BRAIN COMPUTATIONAL MODELING

22 As such, the physical phenomenon of turbulence in fluids has been an object of intense study in the
23 scientific community for more than four centuries, starting from the insightful observations and meticulous
24 drawings by Leonardo Da Vinci (1507) (Deco et al., 2021a) to the mathematical equations developed
25 by Claude-Louis Navier (1823) (Navier, 1823) and eventually refined by George-Gabriel Stokes (Stokes,
26 1843) in order to describe the turbulent regime at the microscopic level. However, as already noticed by Da
27 Vinci, the important properties of turbulence are also to be found at the macroscopic level. One of these
28 properties implies the effective and fast transfer of energy across fluids that Andrey Kolmogorov described
29 in his pioneering phenomenological theory of turbulence (Kolmogorov, 1941a,b). In this ground-breaking
30 work, Kolmogorov introduced the concept of structure functions, which allowed him to quantify the energy
31 cascades that balance kinetics and viscous dissipation based on the correlations between two spatial points
32 in a fluid and, as a result, demonstrate a power scaling law. Importantly, these power laws provide a
33 mathematical foundation for Richardson's earlier concept of cascaded eddies (Richardson, 1922), i.e., a
34 cascade of kinetic energy that is transferred from larger to smaller scales without loss in the so-called
35 inertial subrange. At a more abstract level, effective energy transfer can be considered equivalent to efficient
36 information processing, which makes the study of turbulence in the human brain particularly appealing as
37 it requires the rapid integration of information across spatially distant regions.

38 To study turbulence in a non-hydrodynamic context such as the human brain, one needs to find an
39 appropriate mathematical formalism. In this regard, Yoshiki Kuramoto's theory of coupled oscillators
40 in the 1980s was crucial (Kuramoto, 1984). In fact, using coupled non-linear oscillators, Kuramoto was
41 able to describe turbulence in many different physical systems. Specifically, in the coupled oscillator
42 framework, the Kuramoto local order parameter represents a spatial average of the complex phase factor
43 of the local oscillators weighted by the coupling. Amplitude turbulence is then defined as the standard
44 deviation of the modulus of the Kuramoto local order parameter and can be applied to the empirical data
45 of any physical system, including the human brain. Interestingly, brain activity can be computationally
46 modeled using Stuart-Landau coupled oscillators with a high level of accuracy, therefore providing some
47 degree of convergence with turbulence as originated by Kuramoto's coupled oscillators. Taken together,
48 this motivated the investigation of turbulence in the human brain by combining Kolmogorov's structure
49 functions with Kuramoto's local order parameter as well as building a Hopf whole-brain model with
50 Stuart-Landau oscillators to understand the causal mechanisms given rise to a turbulent regime.

51 The discovery that human brain activity is supported by turbulent dynamics was indeed recently made by
52 using a high-quality large-scale resting-state dataset of 1,003 Human Connectome Project's participants
53 (Deco and Kringelbach, 2020). In that study, we found that the whole-brain dynamics operates in a
54 turbulent regime that follows a consistent power law for functional brain correlations in a broad spatial
55 range similar to that shown by Kolmogorov in fluid dynamics and thus indicative of a cascade of information
56 processing. More recently, using the same dataset, these findings have been extended by incorporating
57 higher-order structure functions showing that out-of-equilibrium turbulent-like brain dynamics are based
58 on the deviations from scale invariance within the phenomenological Kolmogorov's theory (Perl et al.,
59 2023).

60 An important additional consideration in the turbulent dynamics framework concerns the concept of the
61 brain vortex space. In fluid dynamics, the vortices are essentially capturing the rotational kinetic energy. In
62 contrast, the brain vortex space refers to the local level of synchronization at a given spatial scale across

63 spacetime thus capturing the level of rotationality. Based on this central concept, we can define three
64 additional measures to study different aspects of information propagation, namely information transfer,
65 information cascade and information cascade flow. The information transfer indicates how the information
66 travels across space at a specific spatial scale. The other two metrics are interrelated. The information
67 cascade flow measures how the information travels from a given spatial scale to a lower scale in consecutive
68 time steps. The information cascade is the average of the information propagation across spatial scales. It
69 then follows that, by calculating these additional measures, we can provide a richer description of turbulent
70 dynamics and information processing. Since this initial implementation, the turbulent dynamics framework
71 has also helped to discriminate between different brain states in the healthy population and altered states of
72 consciousness (Escrichs et al., 2022; Cruzat et al., 2022; De Filippi et al., 2021), suggesting that is a valid,
73 sensitive and reliable measure. Noteworthy, this framework has also been adapted to direct measures of
74 fast neural dynamics such as resting-state MEG (Deco et al., 2023).

75 The Hopf whole-brain modeling approach also allows to calculate other potential neuroimaging
76 biomarkers based on the brain's reactivity to external *in silico* perturbations. Specifically, one can compute
77 two additional measures: (i) susceptibility, the sensitivity of the whole-brain model to the processing of
78 external stimulations, and (b) information capability, the standard deviation of the difference between the
79 perturbed and unperturbed mean of the modulus of the Kuramoto local order parameter. In the context
80 of turbulence, Deco and Kringelbach (2020) demonstrated that the optimal working point of the Hopf
81 whole-brain model, i.e., showing the best fit to the empirical data, corresponded to a region of maximally
82 developed amplitude turbulence. Remarkably, this was also the point where the information capability
83 reached its maximum, further supporting the notion that amplitude turbulence is key for information
84 processing. It is also important to note that, by incorporating the exponential distance rule (Ercsey-Ravasz
85 et al., 2013) of anatomical connections as a cost-of-wiring principle, the Hopf whole-brain model showed
86 an economy of anatomy that was able to reproduce turbulence. More recent refinements of this model
87 have proved the benefits of adding the rare long-range connections found in the mammalian brain, which
88 improved information processing (Deco et al., 2021b).

89 In this Mini Review, we first describe the findings from our recent study that point to potential
90 neuroimaging biomarkers for TBI using a model-based and model-free approach within the turbulent
91 dynamics framework. Next, we discuss how the model-based approach combined with a simulated attack
92 in that study helped us to understand the effect of structural disconnection. Finally, we propose that deep
93 brain stimulation treatments for TBI could benefit from presurgical assessment of clinical outcomes using
94 whole-brain computational modeling.

2 POTENTIAL NEUROIMAGING BIOMARKERS IN TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY

95 Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) poses a global burden on death and disability only second to cancer according
96 to a recent estimate (Moses et al., 2015), thus representing a significant public health concern. More
97 specifically, recent reports provide an estimate of 50–60 million people with TBI per year worldwide
98 (Feigin et al., 2013). TBI can result from diverse causes including falls, sports injuries, vehicle collisions,
99 intimate partner violence, and military incidents affecting different age groups, from babies to the elderly
100 (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2022). Patients with TBI show a wide
101 spectrum of symptoms, ranging from physical, behavioral and emotional to cognitive (Hoofien et al.,
102 2001; Dikmen et al., 2009; Cantor et al., 2013; Wilde et al., 2022). This wide variation in the clinical
103 manifestations of TBI is likely due to the complexity of the brain's organization, as well as to the patterns
104 and extent of damage caused by external forces leading to TBI. In addition to focal brain damage, rapid

105 acceleration and deceleration forces at the time of brain injury damage the axonal membrane resulting
106 in the so-called diffuse axonal injury (DAI)(Martínez-Molina et al., 2022) that is thought to underlie
107 alterations in brain network connectivity (Sharp et al., 2014). Moreover, DAI and neuroinflammation
108 after TBI might influence the development of neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease
109 (AD), which is a frequent late complication in these patients (Sharp et al., 2014). Given that impairment in
110 executive functioning is one of the most common symptoms after TBI, it is conceivable that DAI affects the
111 long-range connections that shape the brain's information transmission capabilities across time and space
112 (Deco et al., 2021b) and contribute to sustain critical dynamics in the presence of the slow information
113 transfer between neurons (Deco et al., 2023).

114 Historically, patients with TBI have been classified into mild, moderate, and severe diagnostic categories
115 based exclusively on clinical features such as the level of consciousness as evaluated with the Glasgow
116 Coma Scale (GCS) (Teasdale and Jennett, 1974) or duration of post-traumatic amnesia (PTA) (Marshman
117 et al., 2013). However, both the GCS score and the duration of PTA have been shown to be poorly reflective
118 of pathophysiological mechanisms (Zuercher et al., 2009; King et al., 1997). This makes it clear that
119 patients' stratification should be informed by objective measures of pathophysiology such as neuroimaging,
120 neuroelectrophysiological and fluid biomarkers (Majdan et al., 2017; Orešič et al., 2016; Thelin et al., 2019).
121 The discovery of new biomarkers could also help to better monitor the longitudinal progression of TBI and
122 identify patients at high risk for developing neurodegenerative disease secondary to TBI. Although blood
123 biomarkers are accessible cost-effective promising tools for TBI diagnosis and prognosis in primary care
124 settings, they do not allow to assess the brain's abnormality patterns associated with TBI. A multi-modal
125 approach that integrates neuroimaging biomarkers can circumvent this limitation and contribute to provide
126 a more comprehensive understanding of the disease and its progression. Such an approach including
127 biomarker panels combined with machine learning algorithms may help to identify specific injury profiles
128 (Wilde et al., 2022)). In this direction, some studies have started to explore the discriminatory power of
129 a combination of fluid biomarkers in patients with suspected mild TBI with and without neuroimaging
130 findings (Gill et al., 2018; Edwards et al., 2020).

131 Resting-state fMRI (rs-fMRI) data are increasingly being used in the development of new neuroimaging
132 biomarkers for neurological and neuropsychiatric populations (Deco and Kringelbach, 2014) as these
133 sequences have better signal-to-noise ratio compared to task-based studies, can be acquired in patients who
134 may not be able to perform tasks and can be automatically preprocessed with currently available software
135 tools (Whitfield-Gabrieli and Nieto-Castanon, 2012), which can facilitate their translation from research
136 into clinical practice. According to the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), a biomarker can be defined
137 as "a characteristic that is measured as an indicator of normal biological processes, pathogenic processes, or
138 responses to an exposure or intervention, including therapeutic interventions" with the ideal requirements
139 of a biomarker including being sensitive, specific, reproducible and operational among others (Wilde et al.,
140 2022). In this regard, the turbulent dynamics framework holds great promise to provide new neuroimaging
141 biomarkers as: (i) it can be easily computed from rs-fMRI data, (ii) captures global functional brain damage
142 due to structural disconnection at multiple spatial scales, and (iii) reflects regional abnormalities when
143 calculated at node-level providing specific 'fingerprints' potentially useful for distinguishing between
144 different subgroups of patients. This potential is very much in line with the possibility to combine the
145 turbulent framework with the biotype approach, the latter being a data-driven strategy to identify clusters of
146 patients (Brucar et al., 2023). In the field of computational neuropsychiatry, this approach has been used to
147 cluster patients with major depressive disorder based on rs-fMRI data (Drysdale et al., 2017). Interestingly,
148 the authors found different biotypes associated with specific clinical symptoms that showed a differential

149 response to treatment with repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation (rTMS), suggesting the predictive
150 value of the biotype-based classification.

151 In addition to improved diagnosis, the turbulent dynamics framework could also provide prognostic
152 biomarkers to characterize the longitudinal recovery trajectory after TBI. In our recent study (Martínez-
153 Molina et al., 2023), we investigated the potential of the turbulent dynamics framework and whole-brain
154 modeling to provide us with neuroimaging biomarkers that uncover TBI progression during one year
155 of spontaneous recovery using a publicly available rs-fMRI dataset (Roy et al., 2017) with moderate-
156 severe patients at the chronic stage. In our study, we provided evidence of significantly reduced global
157 amplitude turbulence in TBI patients at long distances in the brain, which, as mentioned above, suggests
158 disruptions in the long-range connections that enhance information processing across time and space (Deco
159 et al., 2021b). Node-level turbulence revealed specific resting-state networks 'fingerprints' showing the
160 difference between TBI patients and healthy controls (HCs), which could help to assess the neurobiological
161 effectiveness of targeted treatments. Furthermore, we explored the behavioral relevance of these findings by
162 analyzing the correlation between turbulent brain dynamics and a neuropsychological battery to evaluate
163 executive function focusing on attention and working memory. Our results extended previous findings
164 on the association between metastability and cognitive performance (Hellyer et al., 2015) by showing
165 that, at baseline, working memory scores in TBI patients correlated with information cascade flow and
166 amplitude turbulence in the default mode network at long distances. The results from the model-based
167 approach showed a decrease in the global coupling strength in all time points when fitting the model of
168 TBI patients (Martínez-Molina et al., 2023). TBI patients were also characterized by a U-shaped reduction
169 in the susceptibility and information capability during the one-year recovery trajectory.

170 This promising preliminary evidence could be further refined by examining the relationship between
171 turbulent brain dynamics and genomic information, which would shed light on the neurobiological basis
172 associated with disruptions in the turbulent regime with a particular focus on neuroinflammation. Indeed,
173 the neuroinflammatory response to injury triggered by microglia activation after TBI can persist for
174 months to years (Ramlackhansingh et al., 2011; Shitaka et al., 2011; Johnson et al., 2013). This persistent
175 neuroinflammation might induce the propagation of abnormal proteins, and could be a causal factor in
176 the subsequent neurodegeneration and further cognitive decline often seen after TBI (Gentleman, 2013).
177 Recent studies have started to incorporate the gene expression profiles obtained from blood samples
178 in Alzheimer's disease (AD) patients and investigated their relationship with neuroimaging biomarkers
179 (Zhao et al., 2023). A gene-enrichment analysis revealed that the genes associated with a significant
180 neuroimaging biomarker for AD were involved in immunity-related processes. Given the abovementioned
181 neuroinflammatory response and risk for neurodegeneration after TBI, future gene-enrichment analysis could
182 help to ascertain whether genes associated with neuroinflammation and neurodegeneration might play
183 a role in the underlying neurobiology captured by neuroimaging biomarkers obtained using turbulent
184 dynamics and whole-brain modeling perturbation protocols.

3 WHOLE-BRAIN MODELS TO EVALUATE THE IMPACT OF FOCAL LESIONS AND FOR NEUROSURGICAL PLANNING

185 By simulating normal spontaneous brain function, whole-brain computational modeling can provide
186 a unique tool for understanding and predicting the impact of structural connectivity damage on brain
187 dynamics and, more specifically, the effect of anatomical location and extent of the lesion (Alstott et al.,
188 2009). Such an endeavour is particularly relevant to understand the functional consequences of lesions in
189 stroke (Idesis et al., 2023) and TBI patients (Martínez-Molina et al., 2023), often presenting a heterogeneous

190 pattern of lesions. Using the abovementioned longitudinal rs-fMRI dataset, we applied a simulated attack
191 approach (Medaglia et al., 2022) to explore the influence of focal lesions on the brain's responsiveness to in
192 silico perturbations of the whole-brain model (Martínez-Molina et al., 2023). In brief, the overlap between
193 the patient's specific lesion mask and the parcellation scheme was calculated and used to create a group
194 lesion mask to which we applied two structural disconnection methods: one weighted and one binary, the
195 latter being more aggressive with a full deletion of the lesioned node's connectivity. Both approaches of
196 structural disconnection applied to TBI patients led to decreased reactivity to external perturbations. Of
197 note, the lowest values were found for the most aggressive binary approach. This indicates that, at the
198 group level, the effects of lesions on the brain's reactivity are more prominent when there is a great degree
199 of lesion overlap in the patients under study.

200 Although at present there is no gold standard treatment to promote the recovery of TBI-related cognitive
201 impairments, deep brain stimulation (DBS) within the central lateral (CL) nucleus of the thalamus and
202 the associated medial dorsal tegmental tract has been recently shown to improve executive function in
203 six moderate-severe TBI patients at the chronic stage (Schiff et al., 2023). The CL thalamic neurons
204 project to frontal and striatal regions and might contribute to reverse the cognitive deficits associated with
205 disrupted frontostriatal connectivity after TBI (De Simoni et al., 2018). Despite the beneficial effects of
206 the DBS therapy, there was considerable interindividual variability in the level of efficacy. In this regard,
207 whole-brain computational modeling could help to predict the clinical outcomes of DBS presurgically in
208 order to inform the decision to undergo such an invasive procedure. On the other hand, the selection of
209 the stimulation target was based primarily on their previous work with a single patient in the minimally
210 conscious state (Schiff et al., 2007) and non-human primates studies (Baker et al., 2016; Janson et al., 2021).
211 While this is a scientifically valid approach, whole-brain computational modeling combined with individual
212 structural connectivity could enable the exploration of the optimal brain targets for an individual patient.
213 Although with less spatial resolution than implantable DBS, transcranial temporal interference stimulation
214 (tTIS) (Grossman et al., 2017; Violante et al., 2023) stands as a non-invasive alternative that could also be
215 used to electrically stimulate the striatum (Wessel et al., 2023) and might improve executive dysfunction in
216 TBI patients with altered caudate connectivity (De Simoni et al., 2018). Regardless of the neurostimulation
217 technique used, much more future research is needed before the translation of whole-brain modeling to the
218 clinical setting for optimal brain targeting. In this sense, we envisage three main avenues for future work:
219 (i) improve patient-specific whole-brain computational models to mitigate the impact of overfitting and
220 measurement noise, (ii) study and predict the DBS- or tTIS-induced structural and functional changes as
221 in (van Hartevelt et al., 2014), and (iii) evaluate how well the whole-brain model is able to replicate the
222 changes induced by DBS or tTIS after in silico stimulation of the same brain targets.

4 CONCLUSIONS

223 In summary, in this Mini Review, we have tried to show some progress in the discovery of neuroimaging
224 biomarkers for TBI based on model-free and model-based approaches within the turbulent dynamics
225 framework that have strong potential for application in future clinical practice and treatment trials.
226 The complexity and heterogeneity of TBI calls for a combination of clinical variables and objective
227 pathophysiological biomarkers to improve diagnosis—which to date relies primarily on non-specific
228 clinical evaluations that poorly predict long-term disability—, prognosis and prediction of treatment efficacy.
229 Furthermore, we have discussed how whole-brain computational models can increase our understanding of
230 the effect of focal lesions and to identify optimal stimulation targets which, ultimately, can help to alleviate
231 the long-term suffering associated with TBI.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

232 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
233 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

234 N.M.M.: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Project administration; A.E.: Methodology, Writing
235 – review & editing; Y.S.P.: Methodology, Writing – review & editing; M.L.K.: Conceptualization,
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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Whole-brain turbulent dynamics pipeline and its application to a longitudinal dataset of Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) patients. (A) The implementation of the whole-brain turbulent dynamics framework requires resting-state functional MRI (rs-fMRI), typically using echo-planar images sampling the BOLD time course in each voxel in the brain. This is then combined with a parcellation scheme to recreate the regional time courses for each of the regions in the parcellation, in this case, the fine-grained Schaefer parcellation with 1000 nodes (Schaefer et al., 2018). This allows for the extraction of regional time courses that are used to compute the analytic signal. The Kuramoto local order parameter can define the turbulent signatures of brain activity at different spatial scales in the vortex space. Four turbulent measures based on the Kuramoto local order parameter are calculated as potential neuroimaging biomarkers: amplitude turbulence, information cascade flow, information cascade and information transfer. (B) Left subpanel: Amplitude turbulence differs between TBI patients and healthy controls (HCs) at long distances in the brain over time, peaking at 6 months post-injury. Middle subpanel: Render brains representing the absolute difference of the node-level metastability between HCs and TBI patients at 6 months post-injury for scale $\lambda = 0.03$. Right subpanel: stage-specific resting-state networks "fingerprint" using radar plots for the number of nodes on the top 15% quantile of the absolute difference between HCs and TBI patients at 6-months post-injury comparison for $\lambda = 0.03$. Most of the nodes were ascribed to the SM, DAT and CNT networks. Abbreviations: TR: repetition time; LIM, limbic; CNT, control; DMN, default mode; DAT, dorsal-attention; VAT, ventral attention; VIS, visual; SM, somatosensory. Figure adapted with permission from Martínez-Molina et al. (2023)